

On the evolution of plant thermomorphogenesis

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Additional Information

Extended Figure 4: Copy number of genes involved in thermomorphogenesis signalling in various plant genomes based on the *Arabidopsis thaliana* protein and coding sequences and a combination of HMMER (Potter *et al.*, 2018, HMMER 3.3.2., 2020) and BLASTp (Altschul *et al.*, 1990) searches of available genome and transcriptome data (One Thousand Plant Transcriptomes Initiative, 2019) as in Schumann *et al.* (2011). Species with transcriptome data only are marked with an asterisk. This table contains the same data as Table 1 supplemented by the species marked with asterisks.

Phy - PHYTOCHROME; *CRY* - CRYPTOCHROME; *UVR8* - UVB-RESISTANCE 8; *COP1* - CONSTITUTIVE PHOTOMORPHOGENIC 1; *SPA* - SUPPRESSOR OF PHA-105; *HY5* - ELONGATED HYPOCOTYL 5; *ELF3* - EARLY FLOWERING 3; *PIF* - PHYTOCHROME-INTERACTING FACTOR; *YUC* - YUCCA FLAVIN MONOOXYGENASE; *BZR1* - BRASSINAZOLE-RESISTANT 1

	Phy	CRY	UVR8	COP1	SPA	HY5	ELF3	PIF	YUC	BZR1
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	5	2	1	1	4	2	1	8	11	6
<i>Selaginella moellendorffii</i>	1	3	1	2	1	1	2	2	3	3
<i>Physcomitrium patens</i>	7	1	2	9	2	2	3	4	6	4
<i>Marchantia polymorpha</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	2
<i>Mougeotia sp.*</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
<i>Spirogyra sp.*</i>	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
<i>Natrium digitus*</i>	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
<i>Penium margaritaceum</i>	4	2	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	3
<i>Mesotaenium endlicherianum</i>	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
<i>Spirogloea muscicola</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
<i>Coleochaete irregularis*</i>	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0
<i>Chara braunii</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
<i>Klebsormidium nitens</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
<i>Chlorokybus atmophyticus</i>	2	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
<i>Mesostigma viride</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0

Methods: Search for homologs of thermomorphogenesis signalling genes

For a selection of *Arabidopsis thaliana* genes involved in thermomorphogenesis signalling displayed above and in Table 1 homologs were searched in 11 plant species with available genome data and four species with transcriptome data only, as listed in Table S1. With the exception of *Chlorokybus atmophyticus* and *Mesostigma viride*, the search in all other species was performed on the basis of *A. thaliana* protein sequences, using the HMMER 3.3.2 tools *hmmbuild*, *hmmsearch* and *jackhmmmer* locally or within the HMMER web service (Potter *et al.*, 2018, HMMER 3.3.2., 2020). Later iterations of this process included homologous sequences from *Physcomitrium patens*, *Marchantia polymorpha* and *Chara braunii* together with those of *A. thaliana* in the building of HMM models. Additionally, BLASTp searches were performed (Altschul *et al.*, 1990). Searches in *Chlorokybus atmophyticus* and *Mesostigma viride* were performed on the basis of *A. thaliana* coding sequences by HMMER 3.3.2 tool *nhmmer* (HMMER 3.3.2., 2020) and hits were translated into partial protein sequences. Subsequently, putative homologous sequences were aligned with *A. thaliana* sequences, using MUSCLE 3.8. (Edgar, 2004) for protein multiple sequence alignments. The putative homologous sequences were manually filtered according to sequence similarity and domain structure, which was analyzed via *hmmScan* (HMMER 3.3.2., 2020) against the Pfam protein database (Mistry *et al.*, 2020) and NCBI's Conserved Domain Search (Marchler-Bauer *et al.*, 2015, Lu *et al.*, 2020). The protein sequences assessed as homologous to the here analyzed *A. thaliana* proteins are provided as MUSCLE 3.8. multiple protein sequence alignments in CLUSTAL format and sequence files in FASTA format in Dataset S1 together with Table Dataset_S1_Info (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4945381>) containing the respective sequence IDs and database information.

References (also for databases as cited in Table Dataset_S1_Info)

- Banks JA, Nishiyama T, Hasebe M, et al.** 2011. The Selaginella Genome Identifies Genetic Changes Associated with the Evolution of Vascular Plants. *Science* **332**, 960–963.
- Bowman JL, Kohchi T, Yamato KT, et al.** 2017. Insights into Land Plant Evolution Garnered from the *Marchantia polymorpha* Genome. *Cell* **171**, 287-304.
- Cheng CY, Krishnakumar V, Chan AP, Thibaud-Nissen F, Schobel S, Town CD.** 2017. Araport11: a complete reannotation of the *Arabidopsis thaliana* reference genome. *The Plant journal : for cell and molecular biology* **89**, 789-804.
- Cheng S, Xian W, Fu Y, et al.** 2019. Genomes of Subaerial Zygnematophyceae Provide Insights into Land Plant Evolution. *Cell* **179**, 1057-1067.e14.
- Edgar RC.** 2004. MUSCLE: multiple sequence alignment with high accuracy and high throughput. *Nucleic Acids Research* **32**, 1792-1797
- Grigoriev IV, Hayes RD, Calhoun S, et al.** 2021. PhycoCosm, a comparative algal genomics resource, *Nucleic Acids Research* **49**, D1004–D1011.

HMMER 3.3.2. 2020. <http://hmmer.org/>

Hori K, Maruyama F, Fujisawa T, et al. 2014. Klebsormidium flaccidum genome reveals primary factors for plant terrestrial adaptation. Nature Communication **5**, 978-3978.

Jiao C, Sørensen I, Sun X, et al. 2020. The Penium margaritaceum genome: Hallmarks of the origins of land plants. Cell **181**, 1097-1111.

Lang D, Ullrich KK, Murat F, et al. 2018. The Physcomitrella patens chromosome-scale assembly reveals moss genome structure and evolution. The Plant Journal **93**, 515–533

Liang Z, Geng Y, Ji C, et al. 2020. Mesostigma viride Genome and Transcriptome Provide Insights into the Origin and Evolution of Streptophyta. Advanced Science **7**, 1901850.

Lu S, Wang J, Chitsaz F, et al. 2020. CDD/SPARCLE: the conserved domain database in 2020. Nucleic Acids Research **48**, D265-D268.

Marchler-Bauer A, Derbyshire MK, Gonzales NR, et al. 2015. CDD: NCBI's conserved domain database. Nucleic Acids Research **43**, D222-6.

Merchant SS, Prochnik SE, Vallon O, et al. 2007. The Chlamydomonas Genome Reveals the Evolution of Key Animal and Plant Functions. Science **318**, 245–250.

Mistry J, Chuguransky S, Williams L, et al. 2020. Pfam: The protein families database in 2021. Nucleic Acids Research **49**, D412-D419

One Thousand Transcriptomes Initiative. 2019. One thousand transcriptomes and the phylogenomics of green plants. Nature **574**, 679-685.

Schumann N, Navarro-Quezada AR, Ullrich K, Kuhl C, Quint M. 2011. Molecular Evolution and Selection Patterns of Plant F-box Proteins with C-terminal Kelch Repeats. Plant Physiology **15**, 835-850.

The UniProt Consortium. 2021. UniProt: the universal protein knowledgebase in 2021. Nucleic Acids Research **49**, D1

Wang S, Li L, Li H, et al. 2020. Genomes of early-diverging streptophyte algae shed light on plant terrestrialization. Nature Plants **6**, 95–106